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Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Consistency with Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) Services Projects: Emphasis on Grassroots' Development Needs in Anambra State.

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Consistency with Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) Services Projects: Emphasis on Grassroots' Development Needs in Anambra State. The study was quantitative in nature as data collection was based on the primary sources of data, while the structural functionalism theory was adopted as the analytic framework. The paper examined the MDGs/SGDs and grassroots development in Anambra State, using selected LGAs and communities that cut across the three senatorial districts in the State as the study area. The analysis of data and discussion of findings showed that revealed that the MDG projects were not significantly consistent with grassroots development needs in Anambra State, hence the introduction of SDGs. Apart from the problems of not involving the stakeholders before the decision of what to establish is taken, there were equally cases of massive corrupt practices which stalled the execution of many programmes as well as leading to abandonment of many others, all of which made it extremely difficult for the goals to be realize thereby leaving the people worst of in many places. The study recommended among others that there is the urgent need for the provision of electricity which will uncluck opportunities for people to engage on self-help ventures which have proved to be the most effective strategy against unemployment and poverty, especially the unemployed youth. Obviously, government cannot provide employment for all the army of unemployed youth but government can provide the enabling environment for entrepreneurial activities to thrive. Finally, corruption has remained the bane of the Nigerian society and of course the major reason that Nigeria has been described paradoxically as a rich nation with poor citizens. The government should muster courage to fight corruption so that public funds can be applied to what they are meant for.

Keywords: Development, Goals, Grassroots, Millennium, Sustainable

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of Millennium Development Goals in 2000 necessitated the importance of grassroots development as a veritable means of improving the economic, social and cultural conditions of people in various communities by the government in collaboration with the development partners. One of the ways of bringing the MDGs closer to the people at the grassroots is through the delivery of social services in a satisfactory, timely, effective and adequate manner. In Anambra State, the various state governments initiated numerous strategies and blueprints to achieve MDGs. This is despite the fact that since its inception, the state has experienced a chequered political history which disrupted the structure and

functioning of the body polity and further hindered effective delivery of public goods and services to the grassroots (Nwanolue, Osegbo & Iwuoha, 2012).

The irony is that despite the series of development efforts made by past and present governments on the MDGs, indices in the state still tilt more towards underdevelopment at the grassroots. Poverty is high, especially in the rural areas and slums in the state while unemployment kept soaring. The indices of this sordid situation include poor agricultural productivity; gross infrastructural deficit; rapid population increase; unemployment; lack of social amenities; among others, which had culminated in escalating grassroots poverty and underdevelopment in all ramifications. The people live on the fringe of economic and political corruption, starvation, destitution and ignorance, which undermined their immunity and natural resistance to diseases; such that epidemic continued to kill thousands every year (Odo, 2014).

Despite huge budgetary allocation to the state, infrastructural facilities such as good roads- network, supply of good and adequate water, access roads in rural areas and hinterlands, provision of infrastructure for basic education of its children and youths, healthcare services, transportation services, rural electrification programme and provision of information and communication technology (ICT) to the teeming and yearning people of Anambra State do not seem to be adequate. Government and other organizations have claimed that they have done a lot but the situation currently remains deplorable. Despite the vast amounts of money spent on development efforts in Anambra State by governments and international lending institutions alike in the last two and half decades, many of them have not only failed to stimulate and promote development, but in many cases have been the cause for additional social, economic, and political burdens on grassroots. Many community projects were abandoned half-way due to poor logistics and financial constraint, poor planning and management. Meanwhile, the impact of grassroots development projects under the MDGs in Anambra State has been a great problem due to non-inclusion of detailed participatory framework on the part of government or community leaders at the formulation level of projects that will help to improve the conditions of the rural communities. Also, poor economic conditions, and socially inhibiting cultural practices appeared to have made it impossible for effective and result oriented grassroots development to really take place. Basu (2010) observed that “corruption and unhelpful attitude of the bureaucrats (the governments officials), inordinate delay in getting the wheels of development machinery in motion and poor local population involvements on procedures and formal rules of development projects” (p. 472) has created a lot of hindrances to successful MDGs implementation in the rural areas. Egberi and Madubeze (2014) agreed with this observation, and added that most of the leaders are mired in the pursuit of selfish and personal goals at the expense of broader national interests. Because of the type of political culture in Nigeria, and because the citizens lack knowledge of what the government should be doing for them, they expect little or nothing from the government. They are not interested in what happens in the political system and so the leaders loot the treasury and make policies that are to their own advantage. One doubts whether the State government through its ministries, department and agencies, articulate the grassroots priority needs while planning MDGs projects at the initial stage.

Massive infrastructural requirements based on community priority needs and involvements of the communities do not seem to have been addressed; the mechanism for implementation and the resulting funding gap deteriorates the situation. The rate of urban-rural migration is also high (Chukwuemeka, Okoye-Nebo & Okechukwe, 2013; Enyi, 2014). Hence, MDGs project ownership and sustainability has been a problem in Anambra State. Also, grassroots involvement in project initiation, planning and designing, execution, monitoring and controlling appear not to have received adequate attention in our communities. Consequently, MDGs cannot be said to have performed to expectations in grassroots development across the State. Much as various successive governments in the state have tried to design effective systems in order to enhance grassroots development, none of the attempts have produced the expected results. Research about the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) has tended to view them through the lens of policy-makers and development practitioners. Ignored is the question of how the grassroots who are the ‘targets’ of development programmes experience the MDGs. This has inspired this

work to assess the impact of SDGs on grassroots development in Anambra State so as to suggest measures for improvement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

MDGs, SDGs and Grassroots Development Re-examined

The United Nations Millennium Declaration, signed in September 2000 commits world leaders to combat poverty, hunger, disease, illiteracy, environmental degradation, and discrimination against women. Their importance is highlighted by Biao (2008) who pointed out that the MDGs represent an extraordinary consensus by the international community on the nature of development and on a set of potentially achievable targets. According to World Bank (2010), in one sense they were not new because they had antecedents in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Development Decade of the 1960s and the many United Nations (UN) summits in the second half of the 20th century that set goals for reducing hunger, improving health, eradicating diseases and educating children. Noting that the MDGs are not the first time that global promises have been made about eradicating or rapidly reducing human deprivation.

The concept of sustainable development (SD), according to Mensah and Casadevall (2019) and Ezeokoli et al. (2023), has been widely debated in theoretical importance in areas of social, policy, and academic circles over the years. Although the concept has gained prominence and is famous in theory it tends to be neglected in practice (Ezeokoli et al., 2023; Mensah & Casadevall, 2019). The report of the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987) defined SD as the development that meets the needs of the present without undermining the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. SD is an important concept in today's world and is accepted as the basis for measuring global development (Kioumarsis et al., 2022). The key goal of SD is to achieve environmental equilibrium, economic growth, and social progress (Gossling-Goldsmith, 2018; Zhai & Chang, 2019).

The meaning of the term 'grassroots' is also often clearly defined in a contrast with higher hierarchy levels, not only in a territorial perspective, but very often in the context of a certain organization's hierarchy. Weiping and Jiayi (2011) define the term 'grassroots' as the common or ordinary people in a country, rural regions, rural population, ordinary voters; who are not political office holders. Concurring with the above definitions, Mutisya and Yarime (2011) as well as Jakimow (2011) present grassroots as the local or ordinary people in the geographical point of view as distinct from the active leadership of a party or organization. The grassroots in this sense are seen as average villagers who have the desire, the right and the capability to promote their own welfare and prosperity and to participate in decisions that affect their lives. In essence, grassroots are the common people, especially as contrasted with or separable from the elite group.

Empirical Studies

Globally, numerous studies have been conducted on the MDGs and grassroots development. Some of these studies are presented in this section.

Brinkerhoff (2024) investigates the performance of Cooperate Social Reasonability (CSR) under the MDGs programme. The study conceptualizes Cooperate Social Reasonability (CSR) to include NGOs' activities. He recalled UNDP (2003) which states that MDGs should establish ambitious targets for promoting economic growth, improving health and education, empowering women, creating sustainable development and reducing poverty. He adds that government is not only to be seen as active actor in MDGs (and by extension in SDGs following post 2015), but should structure and influence the contributions of private businesses and NGOs. Brinkerhoff (2004) adds that what the government needs to do is to actively perform its activities under MDGs. It should then create enabling environment for private sector and NGOs to operate. He defines enabling environment as a set of interrelated conditions – such as legal, bureaucratic, fiscal, informational, political and cultural – that impact on the capacity of developmental actors to engage in development process in a sustained and effective manner.

In a related development, a paper by Bussolo and Medvedev (2017) summarizes the policy lessons from applications of the Maquette for MDG Simulations (MAMS) model to two low income countries: Ghana and Honduras. Results show that costs of MDGs achievement could reach 10-13 percent of GDP by 2015,

although, given the observed low productivity in the provision of social services, significant savings may be realized by improving efficiency. Sources of financing also matter: foreign aid inflows can reduce international competitiveness through real exchange appreciation, while domestic financing can crowd out the private sector and slow poverty reduction. Spending a large share of a fixed budget on growth-enhancing infrastructure may mean sacrificing some human development, even if higher growth is usually associated with lower costs of social services. The pursuit of MDGs increases demand for skills: while this encourages higher educational attainments, in the short term this could lead to increased income inequality and a lower poverty elasticity of growth.

Another pertinent study was by Easterly (2007) which presented a critical assessment of how the millennium development goals are unfair to Africa. The author argues that a series of arbitrary choices made in defining “success” or “failure” as achieving numerical targets for the Millennium Development Goals made attainment of the MDGs less likely in Africa than in other regions even when its progress was in line with historical or contemporary experience of other regions. The author found that two-thirds reduction in child mortality is less likely when a continent stands at very high mortality rate, as Africa did. Africa was said to be failing the goal of reducing maternal mortality by two-thirds, but there was no data on maternal mortality trends. The author also noted that Africa was said to be failing to reduce HIV/AIDS, malaria, and TB prevalence, but there was no data on trends in these prevalence rates. Africa was relatively falling behind on reducing the percent without access to clean water, but it would have been relatively catching up if it had been measured the conventional way of percent with access to clean water.

In a related development, Aavik (2007) in his thesis, examine discourses and policies aimed at engendering the UN Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The thesis investigated gender mainstreaming into the MDGs by examining various influences to the UN in incorporating the dimension of gender into the MDGs as well as by considering feminist critique on the MDGs. In doing so, it conducted discourse and content analysis on UN policies and other documents. The thesis discovered that the gender dimension in the MDGs should rather be considered as a reductive reformulation of gender-related commitments adopted in international development conferences since the 1980s, and part of the UN's overall gender mainstreaming efforts, as opposed to involving substantial redefinitions or reorientations that would have emerged shortly before 2000. Further, the research suggests although the UN emphasizes the contribution of the civil society in influencing the preparation process of the MDGs, particularly relating to the inclusion of gender elements in the goals. Their major contribution has involved drawing explicit links between gender and various aspects of poverty and hence emphasizing the importance of considering the gender aspect in MDG- based strategies and policies aimed at alleviating poverty on local and national levels. In addition, the thesis concluded that the MDGs took as their basis the International Development Goals (IDGs), devised by the OECD in 1996, a fact which is not explicitly articulate in the background maternal to the MDGs published by the UN.

Bappenas (2010) whose study is also on Indonesia, said that success in achieving MDGs depends on the achievement of good governance, productive partnerships at all levels of the society. That study found that the government encourages companies to engage in Corporate Social Responsibility by providing tax exemptions in income tax and indirect taxes. She adds that the government sets the Road Map for achieving MDGs and gets the private sector to collaborate. This coordination and harmonization is very important so that CSR activities of private firms do not conflict with government projects or even other forms of activities. She further notes that funding is one of the known problems of MDGs. CSR have the potential of complementing government's efforts. According to her, when one takes a close look at the goals and aspirations of CSR and MDGs, there are indications that CSR can be harmonized with government's programmes to achieve the MDGs. Companies participation in fostering MDGs by implementing CSR will provide some benefits for the companies themselves. Some of such benefits are increased sales and market share, strengthened brand positioning, increased public image and increased profitability.

The literature captures the status of MDGs and grassroots development from the global perspective and the national perspective, the various organizations participating in this process. The literature reviewed examined the concept of grassroots, development and grassroots development. The Millennium development goals, its antecedents and critics were also reviewed. The review of related literature also explored the integration of the MGDs in Nigeria in general and Anambra state in particular. Finally, a review of empirical studies was presented. Attempts were made by many authors to capture the work being done towards accomplishment of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in many countries of the world including Kenya, Namibia, South Africa, Ghana and Nigeria. In all cases, there were mixed reports and findings, the overall effect of MDGS on grassroots development remains unclear. Moreover, in Nigeria, information and research about advancement towards the MDGs remains largely concentrated at the national level, the grassroots were largely ignored. In addition, the previous empirical studies in Nigeria were limited in analyzing few MDG indicators, relied heavily on naive projections and grassroots programme evaluation have been neglected. Whether the level of Anambra State advancement towards the Millennium Development Goals is inadequate for it to achieve the desired targets on the human development parameters by 2015 was not addressed in literature. Besides, none of the studies critically focused on assessing the MDGS and grassroots development by looking at the eight goals simultaneously and data on the status of MDGs in the state since inception was missing. Even the available claims on the effects of MDGs were mostly anecdotal reports from government and its agencies. The voices of the grassroots on the MDGS need to be heard as a way of assessing progress made. These are the gaps in literature. These gaps needs to be addressed and suggested for improvement made so that development will not again elude Anambra State in the post 2015 agenda. To fill these gaps and with the kind of disparities and contrasts that exist in the socio-economic fabric of various states, it seems but natural to have some studies and strategies concentrating on the existing position of states on the MDG parameters and their impact at the grassroots.

Theoretical Orientation

The theoretical framework of analysis in this study rests on the theory of the structural functionalism. DeRosso (2013), structural functionalism, or systems theory, functionalism is a theory that states that societies contain interdependent structure, each of which performs certain functions essential for societal maintenance. It is a framework for building theory that sees society as a complex system whose parts work together to promote solidarity and stability. This approach looks at society through a macro-level orientation, which is a broad focus on the social structures that shape society as a whole, and believes that society has evolved like organisms. This model of political analysis has been more widely used in the sphere of comparative politics because it provides for standard categories for different types of political system.

Functionalism presents a view of social world as essentially harmonious and stable for progressive change. According to Preston (1996), he used functional theory of action to analyze society and other general social system that comprises a set of subsystems that deals with various social sciences such as economics, sociology, politics and psychology. A further explanation by Ugwu and Bako (2014), presented structural-functionalism as a tradition of social analysis that sees society as a mosaic of functions and structures that perform them. For example, in order to survive, a society needs to reduce poverty, educate its children, produce goods, govern its affairs and provide security for its members. These are functions and they necessitate a number of structures such as institutions/agents, industries, parliaments, and so on.

In applying functionalism to this work, the activities of the state government on then MDGs and now SDGs in relation to their relative impacts on the grassroots are examined. The structural system is such that it is from the grassroots that the society and state emerge. Grassroots in Anambra State have physiological needs (reproduction, health, wealth, education, equality, food, shelter, etc) and the government as a political institution exists to meet these needs. Meeting these needs require institutional devices such as then MDGs and present SDGs. When the needs of individuals, who comprise society, are met, then the needs of society are met.

While MDGs was globally-enunciated development benchmarks, SDGs came with a more internationalizing agenda with global ambitions cannot produce on-the-ground change for ordinary citizens or grassroots communities without targeting the programmes at the grassroots. Country-level achievement of the 2015 and beyond with the introduction of SDGs depends on appropriate and effective policies and public spending by both national and sub-national government. By the constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria 1999, the responsibility for MDGs-related public services is shared among the federal, state and local governments. Notable among them are economic planning/management, agriculture, education, health and social welfare.

Given the constitutionally-assigned preoccupation of the federal (central) government with universal or international issues like defence, security, foreign affairs and macroeconomic policies, achieving MDGs in education at whatever level of government, MDGs should represent a balancing of several considerations geared towards transforming the lives of the grassroots people. This can be achieved through the MDGs targets if capital projects are appropriately implemented on projects that directly affect the grassroots. The MDG process can be hindered or accelerated depending on policy synergy and complementary programmes across the three tiers of government. Because Nigeria's states and local governments ideally should be the closest to the grassroots people, in terms of providing basic public services, their actions and inactions could impact greatly on MDGs. It is not enough to mobilize resources for the MDGS as claimed by State documents; the impact of the programmes and projects executed by such resources is equally significant. The fact that resources are limited, government must be disciplined in its choices, scope, and implementation, if budgets are to make the desired impacts on the grassroots.

METHODOLOGY

The design considered most appropriate for the study is descriptive survey design. The choice of the design was largely informed by the fact that a part of the population (sample) would be studied for the purposes of generalizing the result for the entire population of interest.

This paper is to provide a critical assessment of the MDGS as well as its sister programme, SDGs towards grassroots development in Anambra State of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the people of Anambra State. Administratively, the state has twenty-one (21) local government councils and three (3) senatorial districts of North, Central and South. Each senatorial district consists of seven (7) local government areas. Two local government areas were selected purposively from each senatorial district for the study. Purposive selection method was used to ensure that both rural and urban local government areas were reflected in the sample selection for the purposes of achieving balanced opinions from the respondents. By this estimation, 400 becomes the sample size for the study. Furthermore, the number of respondents allocated to each LGA selected for the study was determined through proportionate sampling method. Note that the LGAs included in the sample were purposively selected to reflect urban-rural divide for the needed balanced view to be achieved from the respondents.

The technique used in selecting the respondents within the communities was simple random sampling. This was achieved with the help of table of random numbers. It was considered appropriate to use a probability sampling design at this stage of selection because of the homogeneity that has been achieved in the population. The data for the study came from two main sources namely: primary and secondary sources.

The data generated in the study were analyzed using graphical presentation of the opinions of the respondents given from the interview schedule administered to some community leaders and the test of hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we presented and analyzed the demographic characteristics of the respondents, graphically presented and analyzed the results of the interview with the stakeholders in the communities, answered research question one by means of summary statistics and carried out the test of hypothesis for hypothesis

one to ensure that the answers obtained in research question one did not occur by chance but rather, statistically relevant.

Demographic Features of the Respondents

In this section of the analysis, personal data of the respondents were analyzed and they include gender, marital status of the respondents, age bracket, highest qualification of the respondent, the length of time in years, that the respondents have lived in the current community and the main/primary occupation of the respondents at the time of the survey. The need to analyze these demographic characteristics of the respondents arose so that the suitability of the respondents for the study may be determined. The suitability is in terms of capacity and eligibility for discussing the issues surrounding the MDG projects and grassroots development in Anambra State.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents by Gender

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Male	283	72.8	72.8	72.8
2.	Female	106	27.2	27.2	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The analysis in Table 1 shows that 283 respondents representing 72.8 percent of the sample are male while 27.2 percent are female, thus showing that the sample consists of more males than females.

Table 2: Marital Status of the Respondents

S/N	Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Married	247	63.5	63.5	63.5
2.	Single	88	22.6	22.6	86.1
3.	Widowed	15	3.9	3.9	90.0
4.	Separated	23	5.9	5.9	95.9
5.	Divorced	16	4.1	4.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 2 shows that 247 respondents representing 63.5 percent of the sample are married, 88 representing 22.6 percent are single, 3.9 percent are widowed, 23 representing 5.9 percent are separated and 16 representing 4.1 percent are divorced. The implication of analysis is that greater percentage of the respondents in the sample are in stable family units such that they are in the right frame of mind to discuss the issues under investigation.

Table 3: Distribution of the Respondents According to Age Bracket

S/N	Age Bracket (in years)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	18-24	26	6.7	6.7	6.7
2.	25-34	77	19.8	19.8	26.5
3.	35-44	130	33.5	33.5	60.0
4.	45-54	83	21.3	21.3	81.3
5.	55 and above	73	18.7	18.7	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Apart from the distribution of age of the respondents presented in Table 3, estimation of the average age through the application of arithmetic mean calculation shows that the average age in the sample is 42 years thus indicating that the sample consists of people who are relatively young and as such ought to be active participants in any developmental efforts in the community.

Table 4: Distribution of the Sample by Highest Education Qualification

S/N	Highest Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	High School Certificate	107	27.5	27.5	27.5
2.	Poly/College of Education	135	34.6	34.6	62.1
3.	First Degree	109	28.1	28.1	90.2
4.	Higher Degree	22	5.7	4.7	95.9
5.	Other qualifications	16	4.1	4.1	100.0
Total		389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

As could be seen from Table 4, 107 respondents representing 27.5 percent of the sample said they have high school certificate as their highest educational qualification, 135 of them representing about 34.6 percent said they have polytechnic or College of Education Certificate that is National Diploma (ND) or Higher National Diploma (HND) or National Certificate of Education (NCE). Also, 10.9 representing 28.1 percent of the respondents said they have first degree certificate, 22 representing 5.7 percent said they have higher degree certificate while 16 representing 4.1 percent said they have other qualifications which includes other professional certificates. The implication of the results is that the sample consists of people who are fairly literate and therefore were presumed to be capable of discussing all issues relating to MDGs and grassroots development in Anambra State.

Table 5: Distribution of the Respondents by Length of Time in the Community

S/N	Length of Time (in years)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	0-5	22	5.7	5.7	5.7
2.	6-10	30	7.7	7.7	13.4
3.	11-15	140	36.0	36.0	49.4
4.	16 and above	197	50.6	50.6	100.0
Total		389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The analysis in Table 5 shows that more than 50 percent of the respondents have lived in their current communities for 16 years and more, 36 percent have lived for between 11 and 15 years, 7.7 percent have lived for between 6 and 10 years and 5.7 percent have lived in theirs for 5 years and below. It shows that greater proportion of the sample have lived long enough in their current communities to understand if any developmental projects executed by the MDG in collaboration with the government, has taken place within the period of the study.

Table 6: Distribution of the Respondents by Main/Primary Occupation

S/N	Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Civil/Public Servant	65	16.7	16.7	16.7
2.	Trader	98	25.2	25.2	41.9
3.	Farmer	140	36.0	36.0	77.9
4.	Artisan	44	11.3	11.3	89.2
5.	Politician	30	7.7	7.7	96.9
5.	Retiree	12	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total		389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

As could be seen from Table 6, 140 respondents representing 36 percent of the entire sample said their main or primary occupation is farming, 98 representing 25.2 percent said they are traders, 16.7 percent of them are either civil or public servant and 11.3 percent of them said they are artisans. Interestingly, 30 respondents representing 7.7 percent said their occupation is politics that is, they earn their living primarily from politics. The result as presented shows that government need to support farming activities in the areas of supply of improved seedlings, provision of herbicides, pesticides, fertilizer as well as extension workers services to teach farmers new techniques in farming methods among others. The

implication is that any developmental policy coming from the government should recognize the chunk of those involved in agriculture for the policy to be effective and impact on the people.

Table 6: Opinions on Consistency of MDG Projects with Grassroots Development Needs of the People

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Alternative Responses					Total
		SA	A	D	SD	UND	
1.	Community members are never part of the decision on what project to establish in the community for the benefit of the members.	189 (48.6)	158 (40.6)	27 (6.9)	10 (2.6)	5 (1.3)	389 (100)
2.	Most projects established under the MDG are not the immediate priority of those communities therefore, it was difficult for such project to impact the people.	171 (44.0)	160 (41.1)	32 (8.2)	20 (5.1)	6 (1.5)	389 (100)
3.	There were no adequate mobilization and sensitization of the people to come up with their needs before projects were established.	160 (41.1)	179 (46.0)	35 (9.0)	10 (2.6)	5 (1.3)	389 (100)
4.	Politicians hijacked many of the MDG projects such that many were established where the need for them were relatively very low.	180 (46.3)	150 (38.6)	39 (10.0)	10 (2.6)	10 (2.6)	389 (100)
5.	Many atimes, the implementing officer have diverted funds meant for such projects to personal use because there were no mechanism for monitoring, supervision and evaluation.	162 (41.6)	184 (47.3)	29 (7.5)	10 (2.6)	4 (1.0)	389 (100)
6.	Many of the projects became moribund because the beneficiaries found it difficult to take ownership such that it became unsustainable.	160 (41.1)	189 (48.6)	30 (7.7)	5 (1.3)	5 (1.3)	389 (100)
7.	MDG health related services lacks manpower and essential services hence people finds it more convenient patronizing road side self acclaimed pharmacists.	174 (44.7)	153 (39.3)	40 (10.3)	12 (3.1)	10 (2.6)	389 (100)
8.	Generally, it could be said that there are no commitment in the services provided by the MDG projects across the state.	189 (48.6)	158 (40.6)	27 (6.9)	10 (2.6)	5 (1.3)	389 (100)
9.	The projects/programmes are not adequately funded thereby leading to abandonment syndrome in many cases.	157 (40.4)	188 (48.3)	25 (6.4)	10 (2.6)	9 (2.3)	389 (100)
10.	For MDG projects to impact community development, the beneficiaries (members of the community) must participate in the decision of what to do for them.	160 (41.1)	179 (46.0)	19 (4.9)	21 (5.4)	10 (2.6)	389 (100)
Total		1,702	1,698	303	118	69	389.0
Percentage of Total		(43.8)	(43.7)	(7.8)	(3.0)	(1.8)	(100)

Note: Figures in parenthesis are percentages

: (SA = Strongly agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree, SD = Strongly disagree and UND = Undecided)

Table 5.1 shows that on the average, 43.8 percent of the respondents strongly agreed with all the items, 43.7 percent of them merely agreed, 7.8 percent disagreed, 3 percent strongly disagreed with most of the opinions and 1.8 percent were undecided about all the issues raised in the table. But across the items, there are variations in opinions. For instance, in item 5, 41.6 percent of the respondents strongly agreed and 47.3 percent merely agreed but for item 9, 40.4 percent and 48.3 percent strongly agreed and merely agree respectively.

Table 7: Summary of Chi-square (χ^2) Result for Hypothesis II

Hypothesis	Sample Size (n)	Degrees of freedom (df)	Chi-Square (χ^2) Values		Sig. Level (α)	Decision rule
			$\chi^2_{cal.}$	$\chi^2_{crit.}$		
II	400	36	87.215	43.773	0.05	Rejected

Note: $\chi^2_{cal.}$ means the value of χ^2 calculated and $\chi^2_{crit.}$ means the critical value of χ^2 .

Decision Rule II:

At 0.05 level of significance and 36 degrees of freedom (df), the calculated value of χ^2 (87.215) is greater than the critical value of χ^2 (43.773) (see Appendix II for details of the estimation). Consequently, given the weight of evidence against the null, it was rejected while the alternative which suggests that the MDG projects were not significantly consistent with the grassroots development needs in Anambra State between 2008 and 2015 was accepted.

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

In this section of chapter five, we discussed the findings arising from the analysis of data from the study. The discussion covered the summarized results of the interview with the community leaders, the answers to the research questions as well as the results of the test of hypotheses. The link between the three sections were elaborately discussed to facilitate the desired policy dialogue which are intended to harmonize the MDG projects and grassroots development needs in the state. But more importantly, the discussions were based more on the results of the test of hypotheses.

MDGs and Grassroots Development Policies

The result of the first test of hypothesis indicate that the relationship between the MDGs and grassroots development policies in the State lies in the application of general principle to a particular solution. The result is just a confirmation of the vision of Anambra State under Mr. Peter Obi and now Willie Obiano, where ANIDS and ASSEB were positioned to drive the MDGs. In using such internally designed strategies, it was obvious that the state was determined to achieve the Millennium Development Goals. Particularly with ANIDS which embodied the State Government’s strategic vision by conceptualizing to solve the state’s hydra-headed development problems in an organized, comprehensive and holistic manner by fast-tracking development in all sectors of the state economy simultaneously. Furthermore, the desire to achieve the targets of MDGs could also be seen in the efforts of the government when it took a unique approach of adopting MDGs as its vision in the commitment to grassroots development in the state. As could be seen therefore, both the MDGs and ANIDS are strongly related as our results had shown, in that they both aimed at giving accelerated development to the grassroots. As the United Nations had declared that the goals of MDG is to address a wide variety of issues concerning poverty, education, gender equality, health, the environment and global partnership for development, the Government of Anambra State also resolved to develop all sectors of the state economy simultaneously. Therefore, it becomes the issue of applying a general principle to a particular situation of improving the quality of lives of the population at the community level.

Similarly, the Anambra State Strategic Economic Blueprint (ASSEB) accommodated the MDGs. With its 4Cs strategy which to Continue, Complete, Commission all inherited projects (including MDGs) and then Commence a new set of policies and programs which are in line with the strategy thrust of current administration and the economic pillars and enablers. The economic pillars and enablers are essentially strategies for poverty alleviation and accelerated socio-economic development. They are to encourage and drive high broad-based and sustainable economic development, improve the quality and availability of

social and economic services, to ensure social and economic inclusion of the poor and marginalized groups through targeted programs and finally to vigorously pursue good governance to improve services, their efficiency, accountability and transparency (Anambra State Government, 2015). Therefore, there is apparent linkage between ASSEB and MDGs. In ASSEB, a bold vision is articulated, concrete and measurable targets established for improving governance system, reducing the role of government and limited public intervention, promoting decentralization, increasing the role of private sector for employment generation and income generation activities, increasing the public participation and role of local authorities in local level for effective monitoring, etc. The strategy also emphasizes poverty reduction in all its ramification, especially at the rural areas through good governance, and to also save the lives of those threatened by diseases and hunger which are among the MDGs.

The result is also supported by the relationship between economic empowerment development strategies and MDGs. The economic empowerment development strategies which exists at the national, state, local government, community and individual levels were developed to provide government with a common frame for structuring policies and practices aimed at achieving MDGs targets. The framework was to facilitate speed and efficiency in complying with the MDGs spirit in planning, budgeting and monitoring at all levels of government.

As a medium term development strategies, National Economic Empowerment Development Strategies (NEEDS), and State Economic Empowerment Development Strategies (SEEDS) formed the basis for policy coordination in programmes and projects between the federal government and state governments; and many of the targets in NEEDS and SEEDS were aligned to the MDGs (OSSAP-MDGs, 2008). Furthermore, to extend NEEDS and SEEDS to the grassroots, Local Government's Economic Empowerment Development Strategies (LEEDS) was created. Further down at the community level is the community Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (CEEDS), while at the household level, it is the Personal Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (PEEDS). It is important to note however, that at each of these levels, the pillars remain; empowering people and improving social service delivery; improving the private sector and focusing on non-oil growth; changing the way government works and improving governance; and value reorientation at all levels. However, whether the national, state, local, community and personal development strategies would contribute to the achievement of the MDGs will depend entirely on proper implementation of the policies that have been enunciated to drive the achievement of the MDGs. So the government have vital role to play in ensuring that the policies are purposefully implemented to achieve visible results.

Consistency of MDG/SDG Projects with Grassroots Development

The result of the test of hypothesis in this section suggests that the projects executed to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were not significantly consistent with the development needs of the grassroots in the state. The result is substantially supported by the apparent failure recorded in the process of trying to achieve the goals. As could be seen, government seems to be passionate about improving the living conditions of people, especially the grassroots, by creating different platforms for implementation. Unfortunately, it would appear that turning words into action was difficult for the government. There is a temptation to conclude that all that government had said it would do are more of rhetorics.

From the way that implementation of projects/programmes had been handled, there was nothing to suggest that any of the goals would be achieved as a result, the impact of the policies meant to drive the achievement of the targets was difficult to see at the time of assessment. In fact, the scorecard indicates that there are no signs that the targets could ever be met even if the years of target are extended indefinitely. From the perspective of the respondents, especially the stakeholders (community leaders), community members were never involved in the decision of what project/programme to establish thereby making it easy for wrong projects to be located in the wrong place. Consequently, the projects/programmes did not enjoy as much support and cooperation as they ought to have enjoyed.

They lamented also that among the projects/programmes drawn up to drive the MDGs in the state, power supply was conspicuously absent yet real poverty alleviation process that did not consider electricity

supply as the pivot may not achieve much given the role it plays in self-employment ventures. As a major indicator of economic development, poor power supply or outright absence of it in the development plan, has hindered many small scale businesses which could not afford the alternative source of power from making as much progress as ought to and many have also gone into extinction thereby sending them back to the unemployment market with the consequence of recycling poverty and lack. No wonder that over 40 percent of the community leaders indicated that electricity supply is their top most priority out of the six socio-economic development indicators presented to them.

The state government can embark on rural electrification having seen the crucial role it could play in empowering the grassroots. When provided, the cottage industries and rural entrepreneurship will spring up in their numbers to give employment to the teeming unemployed youth at the community level and at the same time stem the tide of endless rural-urban migration engaged on by the youth who think better opportunities exist in the cities. From the report presented by Idemobi and Ejike (2014) on impact of government projects/programmes on poverty reduction in Anambra State, it was found that many youth were willing to engage on self-help ventures but were always discouraged by the thought of zero power supply and unavailability of micro credit and wished that the government could come to their aid in real terms and not politically motivated empowerment schemes which often collapses as soon as the initiator is out of office.

Educational and health services are also indicators of socio-economic development. As it is, not much can be said to have taken place in the sectors. Although, enrolment at both primary and secondary schools has improved over the past few years, the policy of accessing unhindered free basic education of nine (9) years is yet to be realized as tuition and other masqueraded fees are still being paid at those levels of education. Situation is worst at the early childhood educational level where public schools are almost going into extinction due to the competition they are facing from the privately provided facilities which have proved to be more effective and efficient. Also, health indicators are showing that much has not been done towards the reduction in infant and maternal mortality rates. As the indicators of development, the facilities to implement the policies enunciated to achieve the targets set under the goals are not adequate and so the gap between the policies and actual implementation has to be closed through deliberate efforts by the government. For instance, many primary health care centers have been built through MDG-assisted funds that is, providing the physical building without the necessary equipment and skilled personnel to man the facilities will amount to nothing. This, perhaps, is the major reason that many have chosen to patronize self-acclaimed roadside pharmacists to obtain prescriptions over the counter without minding the dire consequences. In the process, many have died during child-birth and children have also died in their numbers before they reach the age of five or infants dying before they reach twelve months.

The result of our interview section shows that the few available skills acquisition centers are located in the urban areas only. Even at that, they exist virtually in name only as nothing is taught or learnt there due largely to lack of equipment personnel for servicing the centers. Apart from this, people have not been sufficiently sensitized on the alternative means of employment to reduce the pressure on demand for white collar jobs. With concerted efforts, government can create skills acquisition centers across the 21 LGAs in Anambra State, at least one in each LGA to cater for the constituent communities in the LGA and sensitize the people, especially the unemployed on the need to take advantage of such offer as a means of becoming self-reliant. It is an option that had worked perfectly well in many emerging economies across the globe. It would be a more serious approach to skills acquisition and empowerment, especially for the women rather than what obtains at the Women Commission Center Awka, where young women are given some equipment for hair dressing and dress making after about two weeks of being introduced into such trades all in the name of empowerment for self sustenance. The result is that such women usually look for who will buy off the equipment from them after a while because they have not really learnt the art of hair dressing or tailoring to be able to establish on their own.

On the other hand, inadequate funding has characterized the implementation of government policies and MDG's cannot be of exception. However, it must be noted that no meaningful progress can be achieved

without serious financial commitment to project implementations. The government sometimes embarked on many projects which demand a share from the lean financial resources at the same time thereby making some to receive less attention. Sometimes too, funds meant for projects or programmes execution have been diverted into private use on account of corrupt practices with the consequence of either abandoning the projects/programmes or doing a substandard work that have often failed to stand a test of time. Corruption is endemic in our system and it needs to be tackled head on. No nation entrenched in so much ever survives unless some drastic measures are taken to combat the menace. It is common knowledge that corruption has impeded development of Nigeria generally and so far, there have been no serious effort made towards tackling it except for few selective attempts which were targeted at political opponents. But an effective fight against corruption will not spare anybody found to be guilty of it no matter how highly placed or relationship with the authorities. This way, it will be clear to all that the government has come up to end all appearances of corrupt practices in the country. Transparency and accountability are very necessary while handling public funds.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper concluded that the MDG projects were not significantly consistent with grassroots development needs in Anambra State, hence the need to key into the principles of the SDGs. This is confirmed by the level of underdevelopment that exist across the state, especially in the local areas where social amenities are completely absent. Communities were not carried along in the projects/programmes execution process hence their priority areas were not considered the consequence in that many of such projects have not impacted the lives of the people significantly. Apart from the problems of not involving the stakeholders before the decision of what to establish is taken, there were equally cases of massive corrupt practices which stalled the execution of many programmes as well as leading to abandonment of many others, all of which made it extremely difficult for the goals to be realize thereby leaving the people worst of in many places.

From the results of the analysis of data and the discussion of findings, summary and conclusion, we make the following recommendations:

1. Provision of electricity will uncluck opportunities for people to engage on self-help ventures which have proved to be the most effective strategy against unemployment and poverty, especially the unemployed youth. Obviously, government cannot provide employment for all the army of unemployed youth but government can provide the enabling environment for entrepreneurial activities to thrive.
2. Corruption has remained the bane of the Nigerian society and of course the major reason that Nigeria has been described paradoxically as a rich nation with poor citizens. The government should muster courage to fight corruption so that public funds can be applied to what they are meant for.

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